

Water

Veuillez remplir le questionnaire ci-dessous.

Merci !

This part is about tap water in your school. Tap water also includes water from fountains, at canteen for instance. Please tell us how yo agree with the following statements.

	Not agree at all	Rather disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Completely agree
1) Drinking tap water in my school is fine with me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2) The water from my school taps could make me sick	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3) School water taps are generally not clean	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4) The water from my school taps tastes good	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5) My school's tap water contains unhealthy chemicals	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>